

Pursuing a PhD in DH: Challenges, Opportunities, and Best Practices

Abstract

Pursuing a PhD in Digital Humanities (DH) presents unique challenges and opportunities, particularly at the intersection of humanities scholarship and computational methods. This panel brings together five recent and soon PhD graduates from diverse DH backgrounds to discuss experiences from their PhD in Digital Humanities, sharing insights and best practices for both students and supervisors in the field. The speakers will open a discussion on key issues such as integrating computational methods within disciplinary debates and traditions, bridging skill gaps, and finding the most effective forms of dissertation outputs.

Topic Overview and Relevance

As the field of Digital Humanities continues to grow, PhD candidates in this field often face specific obstacles, given the rapid pace of technological development and the academic traditions of the humanities. Early-career researchers may find themselves balancing conflicting demands, such as conducting thorough humanities research while adopting sophisticated computational methods within the constraints of a four-year timeframe. Moreover, educational gaps in computational methodologies and the challenge of aligning DH dissertations with traditional humanities formats (like monographs) add further complexity.

In this panel, recent PhD graduates in DH discuss how they have approached these challenges, exploring possible best practices for students and supervisors alike. The session is aimed at fostering a critical discussion within the DH Benelux community on the best way forward for both PhD students and their supervisors, particularly regarding methodological training, supervision, dissertation structure, and interdisciplinary integration.

Organizers

Lucas van der Deijl (*University of Groningen*)

Lucas is assistant professor in Early Modern Dutch Literature at the University of Groningen, where he also teaches in the MA programme in Digital Humanities. He obtained his PhD in 2022 at the University of Amsterdam, on a computer-assisted study of the first Dutch translations of the New Philosophy (1640-1720).

Milan van Lange (*NIOD Institute for War, Holocaust, and Genocide Studies, Amsterdam*)

Milan works as researcher and program manager of the 'Radical Research and Digital Documents (R2-D2)' team at the NIOD. He is currently investigating the impact of digitisation and recordkeeping practices on historical archives and research. He defended his PhD thesis 'Emotional Imprints: A Computer-assisted Analysis of War-related Emotions in Dutch Parliamentary Debates, 1945–1989' at Utrecht University in 2021.

Alie Lassche (*Center for Humanities Computing, Aarhus University*)

In 2024, Alie obtained her doctoral degree in History at Leiden University. She wrote a dissertation on information dynamics in early modern Dutch chronicles (1500-1860), using a computational approach. She currently works as a postdoctoral researcher at Aarhus University within an interdisciplinary project on the Danish Golden Age.

Ruben Ros (*Leiden University*)

Ruben is a PhD Candidate at the Leiden Center for Digital Humanities and the Institute for History at Leiden University. He is currently finalizing his dissertation on the use of expertise in twentieth-century parliamentary debate.

Kim Smeenk (*University of Groningen*)

Kim is a PhD Candidate at the Research Centre for Media and Journalism Studies at the University of Groningen. She researches the epistemological underpinnings of personal journalism in Dutch national newspapers at the start of the 21st century through a Digital Humanities approach.

Discussion Topics

1. Balancing Humanities Scholarship and Computational Methods

Doctoral candidates in Digital Humanities face the challenge of integrating their research into established disciplinary debates and traditions. This process can be particularly difficult when their digital findings do not neatly align with existing research frameworks, creating a tension between the innovative nature of digital methods and the conventional expectations of their field. Balancing these demands requires careful navigation of both tradition and technological advancement. In this panel, we will discuss this issue and explore strategies for addressing these tensions in DH dissertations.

2. Methodological Skill Gaps in DH PhD Programs

This topic addresses the frequent lack of computational training among DH PhD candidates and examines

ways to bridge this gap through self-study, institutional support, and external training opportunities.

3. Supervision in DH PhDs

Effective supervision is critical in DH, where students often need guidance across multiple domains. We will discuss best practices for supervisors and students alike, focusing on how to facilitate interdisciplinary mentorship and skill development.

4. Publishing in DH: Formats and Outlets

We will discuss various publication strategies for DH PhD students, including the debate between monographs and article-based dissertations, as well as recommendations for identifying suitable journals and other publication outlets.

5. Finding Your Network and Peers

Networking is essential in DH, given the field's interdisciplinary nature. This section will cover ways to connect with peers, mentors, and communities, highlighting the importance of supportive networks in your academic development. We will specifically explore the demand for permanent institutional forms that foster collaboration, networking, and peer-review, like The Swedish National Research School in Data Culture and Society [DASH](#), and the recently established [Society for Computational Humanities Research](#).

Engagement and Interaction

Each topic will be introduced and guided by a dedicated moderator, who may be one of the organizers or an invited collaborator. The moderator will begin with a brief opening statement to frame the discussion. This will be followed by a panel conversation, involving a rotating group of organizers and/or collaborators, and an open dialogue with the audience. By involving different moderators and varied panel compositions for each topic, we aim to reflect the diversity of perspectives within our community. These discussions will serve as a springboard for a broader exchange on best practices for DH PhD candidates.

Challenges and Future Directions for DH Benelux

This panel will raise crucial questions for the DH Benelux community, such as:

- How can DH programs better address the methodological skills gap?
- What is the most effective dissertation format for DH research, and how can the community standardize

this?

- Should DH education and support be more systematically organized across the Benelux?

Through these discussions, we aim to contribute to an ongoing dialogue in the DH Benelux community about supporting PhD candidates and advancing DH education standards.

Schedule

General introduction: Milan van Lange

1. Balancing Humanities Scholarship and Computational Methods

Moderator: Antonios Lagarias

Panelists: Evelien de Graaf, Yahui Zhao, and Loren Verreyen

2. Methodological Skill Gaps in DH PhD Programs

Moderator: Marijke Beersmans

Panelists: Sofie Moors, Antonios Lagarias, and Evelien de Graaf

3. Supervision in DH PhDs

Moderator: Anthe Sevenants

Panelists: Josie Lauferts, Milan van Lange, and Aron van de Pol

4. Publishing in DH: Formats and Outlets

Moderator: Aron van de Pol

Panelists: Anthe Sevenants, Ruben Ros, and Alie Lassche

5. Finding Your Network and Peers

Moderator: Ruben Ros

Panelists: Milan van Lange, Alie Lassche, and Lucas van der Deijl

Closing statement and general moderation: Lucas van der Deijl
